

THE PHILIPPINE INCOME TAX: INVESTIGATING THE INFLUENCE OF PUBLIC MANAGEMENT ON CITIZEN COMPLIANCE

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the factors influencing tax compliance by assessing taxpayers' perceptions of fairness, system complexity, government transparency, and the perceived benefits of tax-funded public services. Using a descriptive–correlational research design, the study gathered quantitative data through a structured survey administered to taxpayers within the selected locality. Weighted means were computed to determine the level of agreement on various compliance statements, while p-values were used to test the significance of relationships between identified factors and taxpayers' compliance behaviors. Data analysis followed standard statistical procedures, including descriptive statistics and hypothesis testing at a 0.05 level of significance. Results revealed that taxpayers generally agreed that fairness in tax rates, simplification of procedures, and confidence in the appropriate implementation of the tax system positively influence compliance. However, some factors—such as convenience in accessing government services or perceptions of infrastructure projects—did not show significant associations with compliance. The findings indicate that perceptions of fairness and system effectiveness remain the strongest predictors of taxpayers' willingness to comply, whereas factors related to service accessibility and visibility of public outputs may not directly shape compliance behavior. The study recommends continuing reforms that promote transparency, simplify tax processes, and strengthen public trust to enhance compliance rates.

Keywords: *tax compliance, perceived fairness, tax system complexity, public trust, government transparency, public services*

INTRODUCTION

Taxation serves as a fundamental mechanism through which governments generate revenue to sustain public services such as education, health care, infrastructure, and social welfare. Governments rely heavily on tax collections to maintain adequate financial resources for fulfilling their mandates. In the Philippines, taxation has long been regarded as the lifeblood of government, with the Supreme Court reiterating in *National Power Corporation v. City of Cabanatuan* (G.R. No. 149110, 2003) that the power to tax arises from the necessity to promote public welfare. An effective tax system requires a cooperative relationship between the state and its citizens, guided by the 1987 Philippine Constitution, which mandates that taxation must be uniform and equitable.

Research highlights the intersection of public finance, tax administration, and taxpayer behavior in shaping national development. Tax reforms, such as the Tax Reform for Acceleration and Inclusion (TRAIN) Law, have generated debates on equity and burden distribution (Department of Finance, 2018). Despite recorded revenue growth—for instance, a 9.3% increase in 2021 (Noble, 2021)—the Philippines continues to face significant fiscal deficits (Cordero, 2022). International evidence suggests that taxpayer compliance is influenced by perceived fairness, trust in government, simplicity of processes, and taxpayer education (De Neve et al., 2020). However, less attention has been given to how public management practices, particularly the visible implementation of taxation principles, shape Filipino taxpayers' compliance. This gap underscores the need to explore how the Philippine tax system aligns with classical canons of taxation and how public management affects citizen behavior.

Despite modernization efforts—such as BIR awareness campaigns and digital filing systems—tax compliance in the Philippines remains inconsistent. Many citizens lack sufficient understanding of tax laws due to curriculum changes that removed tertiary-level taxation subjects from the General Education program (Commission on Higher Education, 2013). Misconceptions about fairness, transparency, and government spending further contribute to skepticism, particularly among small business owners, self-employed individuals, and young professionals. Given the role of taxation in post-pandemic recovery, there is a pressing need to examine how public management, citizens' perceptions, and adherence to taxation principles interact to influence compliance. Understanding these elements justifies the study's focus on exploring the perceived effectiveness of tax authorities and the factors that drive or hinder taxpayer compliance.

Research consistently emphasizes that taxpayers' perceptions of fairness and justice are central to voluntary compliance. Taxpayers are more willing to comply when they perceive the tax system as equitable, both in distributing the tax burden (distributive justice) and ensuring impartial treatment during enforcement (procedural justice) (Kirchler et al., 2008; MDPI, 2024). Procedural fairness, transparency, and impartial administration positively

influence compliance (Kirchler et al., 2008). In the Philippines, perceptions of fairness motivate taxpayers to comply when revenues are perceived as supporting public services and societal benefits (Pacaldo & Ferrer, 2020). This aligns with assessing adherence to Adam Smith's canons of taxation, particularly equity and fairness.

Trust in government and public institutions is another key determinant of tax compliance. According to the "slippery slope framework," taxpayers comply voluntarily when they trust authorities, while strict enforcement primarily ensures compliance through coercion (Wahl et al., 2010). Philippine studies indicate that among firms, trust has a stronger influence on tax morale than enforcement alone (Pacaldo & Ferrer, 2020). This supports examining the relationship between perceived public management effectiveness—including fairness, transparency, and accountability—and taxpayer behavior.

Taxpayer awareness of obligations, rights, exemptions, and payment mechanisms strongly affects compliance behavior. Citizens with greater understanding of tax policies and access to efficient systems, such as e-payment, are more likely to comply voluntarily (RSIS International, 2023; ILOMATA, 2024). Convenience and administrative efficiency reduce compliance costs, making adherence easier, highlighting the importance of service-oriented public management (Kirchler et al., 2008).

Studies in the Philippines and internationally show that governance quality, institutional transparency, service delivery, and visible public projects positively influence compliance (Springer, 2024; MDPI, 2024). Citizens are more likely to fulfill tax obligations when they perceive government as legitimate, effective, and responsive. Public management effectiveness extends beyond enforcement to include trust-building, fair administration, and quality service provision, framing the study's focus on how public management shapes taxpayer perceptions and compliance (Wahl et al., 2010; Yip & Ho, 2021).

Despite extensive literature, gaps remain regarding individual income taxpayers in the Philippines, as most studies focus on firm-level compliance (Pacaldo & Ferrer, 2020). Limited research examines the relationship between taxpayers' perceptions, adherence to classical tax canons (equity, certainty, convenience, economy), and public management effectiveness (Kirchler et al., 2008; MDPI, 2024). This study addresses these gaps by exploring how perceptions of fairness, transparency, trust, enforcement, service quality, and government projects influence individual taxpayers' compliance behavior, providing insights for improving voluntary compliance, strengthening trust, and enhancing public management effectiveness (Wahl et al., 2010; Yip & Ho, 2021).

Taxpayers' perceptions of fairness, equity, and procedural justice are central to voluntary compliance. Trust in government strengthens compliance, often more than strict enforcement. Awareness, knowledge, and accessibility reduce compliance costs, while good governance, transparency, and visible public projects enhance legitimacy and effectiveness. Yet, research on individual income taxpayers and the direct relationship between classical tax canons and public management remains limited, warranting further study.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore the factors that influence citizen compliance with the personal income tax system in the Philippines. The study sought to understand how citizens perceive the Philippine personal income tax system and the degree to which the system adhered to the principles of taxation. Answers to the following research questions were sought:

1. How do the respondents perceive the Philippine personal income tax system, particularly in relation to:
 - 1.1. tax amount and tax exemptions,
 - 1.2. tax compliance and awareness,
 - 1.3. tax fairness, equity and transparency?
2. To what extent do the respondents perceive Philippine Income Tax System adherence to the Canon of Taxation principles as follows:
 - 2.1. taxpayers' pay depends on their ability to pay,
 - 2.2. taxes to be paid should not be arbitrary,
 - 2.3. the method and timing of tax payment should be convenient, and
 - 2.4. the expense of tax collection should not be excessive?
3. What are the perceived factors that influence Philippine taxpayer compliance as per consensus of the respondents?
 - 3.1. perceived fairness
 - 3.2. penalties and enforcement
 - 3.3. taxpayer education
 - 3.4. simple process of income tax collection
 - 3.5. access to services
 - 3.6. trust in government
 - 3.7. government projects
4. Is there a significant relationship between the perception of Philippine income tax and perception of adherence to the Canon of taxation principles?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived effectiveness in public management and perceived income tax compliance rate of taxpayers?
6. What recommendations can be derived from the study's findings to strengthen the impact of public management on citizen income tax compliance?

METHODOLOGY

Research Method Used

A quantitative approach was employed to collect and analyze numerical data. A descriptive survey gathered respondents' perceptions of the Philippine personal income tax system, its adherence to the canon of taxation, and factors influencing taxpayer compliance. A correlational design determined relationships between factors affecting compliance, awareness of tax-related information, and public management behavior.

Interviews were conducted to support the quantitative data, with responses transcribed, coded, and grouped into themes to strengthen survey findings.

Population Frame and Sampling Scheme

Respondents were selected from Metro Manila, Region III, and Region IV-A, targeting individuals employed in public or private institutions or running their own businesses, excluding direct involvement in tax authorities. A total of 400 respondents were randomly selected, ensuring voluntary participation. Twenty respondents from the survey were purposively chosen for interviews to provide qualitative insights. Selection ensured diversity in employment status and income sources without restrictions on tenure or business type.

Description of the Respondents

The sample included 243 females and 157 males, mostly aged 20-29. Educational attainment ranged from elementary to postgraduate, with the majority being college graduates. Monthly salaries varied from below PHP10,000 to above PHP40,000. Most respondents were employed (267), while 133 were self-employed. The majority worked full-time in the private sector (308), primarily in NCR (223), Region IV-A (168), and Region III (9).

Research Instruments Used

A researcher-made survey was used, consisting of three sections: Part I captured demographics; Part II assessed perceptions of the income tax system, adherence to taxation principles, and factors influencing compliance. Section A had 20 items on tax perception, Section B had 10 items on tax principles, and Section C included 25 factors affecting compliance. Instruments were reviewed by panel members and the adviser, followed by pilot testing with 10 respondents. Cronbach's alpha of 0.97 indicated excellent reliability. An interview guide, validated similarly, captured qualitative perceptions. A 5-point Likert scale was used to measure responses.

Data-Gathering Procedures

Permission was obtained from agencies and participants before data collection. Surveys were distributed online via Google Forms and face-to-face, ensuring voluntary participation, confidentiality, and informed consent. Interviews were conducted with 3 respondents face-to-face and 17 via phone, scheduled at respondents' convenience. All participants were briefed on recording, consent, confidentiality, and their right to withdraw. Data were carefully checked for completeness before encoding for analysis.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Quantitative data were analyzed using mean, multiple regression, and Pearson r correlation. Mean was used to summarize responses for key survey items. Multiple

regression examined the relationship between tax perception and adherence to taxation principles, while Pearson r assessed the relationship between perceived public management effectiveness and income tax compliance.

RESULTS

Respondents Perceive the Personal Income Tax System

Table 1. Respondents' Perception in Terms of Tax Amounts and Tax Exemption

	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I have a comprehensive understanding of the personal income tax system of the Philippines, including its different components and regulation	3.44	Agree
2. I possess a thorough understanding of the key concepts and terminologies involved in taxation, which helps me navigate the system better	3.24	Neither Agree or Disagree
3. I am adept at computing my own taxes, including understanding the tax brackets, deductions, and exemptions that apply to my income.	3.01	Neither Agree or Disagree
4. I understand the tax exemptions applied in my tax computation because I try to educate myself, and materials about it are available.	3.51	Agree
5. I comply with paying my taxes regardless of their rate and rules because I know it's my responsibility.	3.83	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.41	Agree

Legend: 1 = 4.21-5.00, Strongly Agree (SA); 2 = 3.41-4.20, Agree (A); 3 = 2.61-3.40, Neither Agree or Disagree (NAD); 4 = 1.81-2.60, Disagree (D); 1.00=1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 1 presents the respondents' perceptions regarding tax amounts and tax exemptions in the Philippine personal income tax system. The overall weighted mean of 3.41, verbally interpreted as "Agree," indicates that respondents generally feel knowledgeable and responsible about their tax obligations.

Table 2. Respondents' Perception in Terms of Tax Compliance and Awareness

	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
6. I prioritize following tax laws because I understand the importance of compliance and the negative consequences that come with non-compliance.	3.67	Agree
7. While I comply with the tax system, I also recognize the need for continuous improvement and critical evaluation of its effectiveness and fairness	3.83	Agree
8. I prioritize paying my taxes on time and in full, as I am aware that non-payment can result in penalties, interest, and legal action by the government.	3.87	Agree
9. I am aware of the penalties and consequences that come with non-compliance, including fines, interest, and legal action, and I prioritize following tax laws accordingly.	3.86	Agree

10. I am aware that ignoring tax laws can have a negative impact on my income and financial stability, and I take steps to educate myself and stay informed about any updates or changes in the system.	3.95	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.84	Agree

Legend: 1 = 4.21-5.00, Strongly Agree (SA); 2 = 3.41–4.20, Agree (A); 3 = 2.61–3.40, Neither Agree or Disagree (NAD); 4 = 1.81–2.60, Disagree (D); 1.00=1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 2 presents the respondents' perceptions regarding tax compliance and awareness in the Philippine personal income tax system. The overall weighted mean of 3.84, verbally interpreted as "Agree," suggests that respondents generally prioritize complying with tax laws, understand the consequences of non-compliance, and actively seek information to stay informed about tax regulations.

Table 3. Respondents' Perception in Terms of Tax Fairness, Equity and Transparency

	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
11. I support taxation but have concerns about the government's tax collection methods and believe there is room for improvement in transparency, efficiency, and fairness.	4.04	Agree
12. I am dissatisfied with how the administration handles tax problems, and I believe there is a need for more proactive and effective measures to address tax-related issues.	3.93	Agree
13. I strongly endorse personal income tax's critical role in the country's development and support the government's efforts to enhance transparency, fairness, and efficiency in the system.	3.79	Agree
14. I believe that there is transparency where my taxes are used by the government through services I am able to access.	3.21	Neither Agree or Disagree
15. The taxes imposed by the tax administration is reasonable and just.	3.17	Neither Agree or Disagree
16. I do not doubt that my taxes will be misused because I can see and track my tax records.	3.04	Neither Agree or Disagree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.53	Agree

Legend: 1 = 4.21-5.00, Strongly Agree (SA); 2 = 3.41–4.20, Agree (A); 3 = 2.61–3.40, Neither Agree or Disagree (NAD); 4 = 1.81–2.60, Disagree (D); 1.00=1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 3 presents the respondents' perceptions regarding the fairness, transparency, and effectiveness of the Philippine personal income tax system. The overall weighted mean of 3.53, verbally interpreted as "Agree," indicates that while respondents recognize the importance of taxation and generally support government efforts, some express concerns about transparency, efficiency, and fairness in tax administration.

The Extent to which the Respondents Perceive the Philippine Income Tax System's Adherence to the Canon of Taxation Principles

Table 4. Perception on Philippine Income Tax System Adherence to the Canon of Taxation Principles

	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The tax system considers citizen income for tax payments.	3.59	Agree
2. The tax system burdens low-income earners compared to high-income earners.	3.55	Agree
3. Taxes are mandatory and enforced.	3.89	Agree
4. The tax system is not consultative.	3.52	Agree
5. The tax system is too complicated for common people.	3.70	Agree
6. The time for tax filing is too short.	3.35	Neither Agree or Disagree
7. Self-employed individuals face inconvenient tax filing requirements.	3.64	Agree
8. Tax filing for an employed individual is easy because it's handled by the employer.	3.89	Agree
9. Tax collection is not proportional to citizens' income.	3.57	Agree
10. Citizens perceive taxes as excessive and do not feel that they benefit from them.	3.75	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.57	Agree

Legend: 1 = 4.21-5.00, Strongly Agree (SA); 2 = 3.41-4.20, Agree (A); 3 = 2.61-3.40, Neither Agree or Disagree (NAD); 4 = 1.81-2.60, Disagree (D); 1.00-1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 4 presents the respondents' perceptions of the Philippine personal income tax system in terms of equity, convenience, and administrative efficiency. The overall weighted mean of 3.57, verbally interpreted as "Agree," indicates that respondents generally recognize the system's fairness and mandatory nature, though some perceive complications in filing and inconvenience for certain taxpayers, particularly the self-employed.

The Factors That Influence Philippine Taxpayer Compliance As Perceived by The Respondents

Table 5. Respondents' Consensus on Perceived Factors Influencing Tax Compliance

Statements Corresponding to Compliance Factors	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Compliance due to Perceived Fairness and Simplification of Tax System		
1. Willingness to pay due to fairness of tax rate distribution or bracketing.	3.60	Agree
2. The complexity of the tax system affects compliance.	3.60	Agree
3. Appropriate and effective tax system approved by the government.	3.60	Agree
4. Easy implementation of the tax system promotes compliance.	3.60	Agree
5. A simple and easy tax payment procedure allows immediate compliance.	3.60	Agree

Statements Corresponding to Compliance Factors	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Compliance due to Consequences/Penalties and Enforcement		
6. Automatic tax deductions leave no choice but to pay.	4.12	Agree
7. Compliance to avoid hassle or penalty.	4.12	Agree
8. Compliance to avoid penalties for tax evasion.	4.12	Agree
9. Compliance to avoid legal consequences for tax evasion.	4.12	Agree
Compliance is Perceived as Responsibility/Citizenship due to Tax Knowledge		
10. Understanding responsibility as a citizen drives compliance.	3.81	Agree
11. Paying taxes is seen as the right thing to do.	3.81	Agree
12. Compliance is due to the necessity of taxes for the country to function.	3.81	Agree
13. The belief is that taxes contribute to the country's growth.	3.81	Agree
Compliance due to Governments' Education and Information		
14. Compliance due to government education efforts.	3.31	Neither Agree nor Disagree
15. Reliable information dissemination by the government about tax-related issues.	3.31	Neither Agree nor Disagree
Compliance due to Trust in Government		
16. Trust in the government's good faith use of tax collection.	3.21	Neither Agree nor Disagree
17. Trust in the government's use of taxes through visible projects.	3.21	Neither Agree nor Disagree
18. Trust in the government's handling of taxes leads to diligent payment.	3.21	Neither Agree nor Disagree
19. Government shows good examples in tax collection processes.	3.21	Neither Agree nor Disagree
20. Trustworthy tax computation by the government.	3.21	Neither Agree nor Disagree
Compliance because of Materialized Government Projects, Programs, and Accessible Services		
21. The belief is that taxes will benefit citizens through public interest projects.	3.42	Agree
22. Easy access to government services and friendly-environment due to diligent tax payment.	3.42	Agree
23. Infrastructure projects were seen as a product of taxes paid.	3.42	Agree
24. Government offices provide quality service that equals the tax I'm paying for.	3.42	Agree
25. I benefit from projects for the socio-economic development of the government as a result of tax payments.	3.42	Agree
Overall Mean	3.58	Agree

Legend: 1 = 4.21-5.00, Strongly Agree (SA); 2 = 3.41-4.20, Agree (A); 3 = 2.61-3.40, Neither Agree or Disagree (NAD); 4 = 1.81-2.60, Disagree (D); 1.00-1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 5 presents the respondents' consensus on the factors influencing tax compliance in the Philippines. The overall weighted mean of 3.58, verbally interpreted as "Agree," suggests that taxpayers generally comply due to a combination of perceived fairness, enforcement mechanisms, civic responsibility, and the tangible benefits derived from government projects and services.

The Significant Relationship Between the Perception of Philippine Income Tax and the Perception of Adherence To the Canon of Taxation Principles

Table 6. The Relationship Between the Perception of Philippine Income Tax and the Perception of Adherence to the Canon of Taxation Principles

p-value	Level of Significance	Decision
0.292	0.050	Failed to reject H ₀

Legend: P < 0.05 -Significant (S) P > 0.05 – Not Significant (NS)

Table 6 shows that there is no significant relationship and there is a low correlation between the perception of Philippine income tax and the perception of adherence to Canon of taxation principles

The Significant Relationship Between the Perceived Effectiveness in Public Management and Perceived Income Tax Compliance Rate of Taxpayers

Table 7. Public Management's Perceived Effectiveness and its Relationship to the Tax Compliance Rate

(DV1-TC1) 4. I prioritize following tax laws because I understand the importance of compliance and the negative consequences that come with non-compliance.

Independent Variable	p-value	Level of Significance	Decision
26. The belief is that taxes will benefit citizens through public interest projects.	0.000	0.05	Reject H ₀
27. Easy access to government services and friendly environment due to diligent tax payment.	0.701	0.05	Failed to reject H ₀
28. Infrastructure projects were seen as a product of taxes paid.	0.332	0.05	Failed to reject H ₀
29. Government offices provide quality service that equals the tax I'm paying for.	0.445	0.05	Failed to reject H ₀
30. I benefit from projects for the socio-economic development of the government as a result of tax payments.	0.256	0.05	Failed to reject H ₀

(DV2-TC2) 5. While I comply with the tax system, I also recognize the need for continuous improvement and critical evaluation of its effectiveness and fairness.

Independent Variable	p-value	Level of Significance	Decision
31. The belief is that taxes will benefit citizens through public interest projects.	0.002	0.05	Reject H ₀
32. Easy access to government services and friendly-environment due to diligent tax payment.	0.288	0.05	Failed to reject H ₀
33. Infrastructure projects were seen as a product of taxes paid.	0.096	0.05	Failed to reject H ₀
34. Government offices provide quality service that equals the tax I'm paying for.	0.019	0.05	Reject H ₀
35. I benefit from projects for the socio-economic development of the government as a result of tax payments.	0.138	0.05	Failed to reject H ₀

(DV3—TC3) 6. I prioritize paying my taxes on time and in full, as I am aware that non-payment can result in penalties, interest, and legal action by the government.

Independent Variable	p-value	Level of Significance	Decision
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36. The belief is that taxes will benefit citizens through public interest projects.	0.000	0.05	Reject H 0
37. Easy access to government services and friendly-environment due to diligent tax payment.	0.143	0.05	Failed to reject H 0
38. Infrastructure projects were seen as a product of taxes paid.	0.433	0.05	Failed to reject H 0
39. Government offices provide quality service that equals the tax I'm paying for.	0.082	0.05	Failed to reject H 0
40. I benefit from projects for the socio-economic development of the government as a result of tax payments.	0.555	0.05	Failed to reject H 0

Legend: P < 0.05 -Significant (S) P > 0.05 – Not Significant (NS)

Table 7 shows the relationship between perceptions of government projects, programs, and services and adherence to taxation principles. Only the belief that taxes benefit citizens through public interest projects ($p = 0.000$) was significantly related, while the other factors showed no significant relationship ($p > 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

Respondents' Perception in Terms of Tax Amounts and Tax Exemption

Table 1 shows that respondents generally have a positive perception of their understanding and compliance with the Philippine personal income tax system, with an overall weighted mean of 3.41 (*Agree*). Respondents agreed (3.44) that they understand the system's components and regulations, reflecting awareness that supports compliance, consistent with prior studies emphasizing knowledge as a key driver of voluntary adherence (Kirchler et al., 2008; RSIS International, 2023).

Lower scores on understanding key concepts (3.24) and computing taxes (3.01) highlight gaps in practical application, echoing literature on limited taxation education in the Philippines (Commission on Higher Education, 2013). Yet, respondents agreed (3.51) that they understand tax exemptions due to proactive learning and available materials, demonstrating the importance of accessible resources and service-oriented public management in facilitating compliance.

The highest agreement (3.83) was observed for complying with taxes as a civic duty, aligning with the concept of tax morale, where perceptions of fairness, trust in government, and civic responsibility encourage voluntary compliance (Pacaldo & Ferrer, 2020; Wahl et al., 2010).

Overall, the findings suggest that while Filipino taxpayers are generally aware of the system and motivated by responsibility, gaps remain in practical knowledge and computation skills. Enhancing taxpayer education, simplifying procedures, and ensuring transparency can strengthen compliance, equity, and trust, reinforcing the classical canons of taxation and effective public management.

Respondents' Perception in Terms of Tax Compliance and Awareness

Table 2 shows that respondents exhibit a high level of compliance and awareness, with an overall weighted mean of 3.84 (*Agree*). Respondents recognize the importance of adhering to tax laws, understanding both the negative consequences of non-compliance and the broader role of taxes in supporting public services.

Specifically, respondents agreed that they prioritize compliance due to awareness of penalties and legal consequences (3.67–3.87), and they actively seek to stay informed about tax updates and their financial implications (3.95). These findings align with literature emphasizing that knowledge of obligations, risks, and the systemic importance of taxes significantly enhances voluntary compliance (Kirchler et al., 2008; Wahl et al., 2010; Pacaldo & Ferrer, 2020).

Moreover, respondents acknowledged the need for continuous evaluation and improvement of the tax system (3.83), indicating a critical and responsible approach to civic duties. This highlights that compliance is not merely reactive but informed by understanding, reflection, and engagement with public management processes.

The results suggest that Filipino taxpayers are generally well-informed and motivated to comply, especially when aware of legal repercussions and the benefits of taxation. This reinforces the role of taxpayer education, transparency, and effective governance in fostering voluntary compliance, trust, and adherence to the canons of taxation, particularly certainty, equity, and convenience.

Respondents' Perception in Terms of Tax Fairness, Equity and Transparency

Table 3 shows that respondents generally perceive the tax system as fair and important, with an overall weighted mean of 3.53 (*Agree*). Respondents agree that taxation is essential for national development and support efforts to enhance transparency, fairness, and efficiency (3.79–4.04). They also recognize the need for improvements in government administration and proactive measures to address tax-related issues (3.93), reflecting a desire for accountability and better governance.

However, moderate responses were observed regarding direct visibility of tax use, reasonableness of taxes, and confidence in proper utilization of funds (3.04–3.21, *Neither Agree nor Disagree*). This indicates some skepticism among taxpayers about whether taxes are fully allocated transparently and equitably, consistent with studies highlighting the influence of perceived fairness and procedural justice on tax morale (Kirchler et al., 2008; Pacaldo & Ferrer, 2020).

Overall, the data suggest that while taxpayers appreciate the role of personal income taxes and support fair administration, gaps in perceived transparency and equity remain. Enhancing visible accountability, tracking mechanisms, and fair enforcement can strengthen trust, compliance, and adherence to the canons of taxation, particularly equity and certainty.

Perception on Philippine Income Tax System Adherence to the Canon of Taxation Principles

Table 4 indicates that respondents generally perceive the Philippine income tax system as partially aligned with the classical canons of taxation, with an overall weighted mean of 3.57 (*Agree*). Respondents agree that the system considers citizen income, mandates compliance, and enforces taxes (3.55–3.89). They also recognize challenges, such as complexity, inconvenient filing for self-employed individuals, and insufficient consultation (3.52–3.70), highlighting areas where the canons of certainty, convenience, and equity are not fully realized.

Moderate agreement was noted regarding short filing periods (3.35, *Neither Agree nor Disagree*), suggesting mixed perceptions about procedural efficiency. Additionally, respondents perceive taxation as burdensome, especially for low-income earners, and feel that taxes may not provide proportional benefits (3.57–3.75), emphasizing concerns about equity and fairness in practice.

Overall, while the tax system demonstrates mandatory enforcement and structural considerations, gaps remain in simplicity, consultation, and perceived proportionality of benefits. Addressing these gaps through better public management, simplification of procedures, and transparent communication can strengthen alignment with Adam Smith's canons, improve taxpayer trust, and enhance voluntary compliance (Kirchler et al., 2008; MDPI, 2024).

Respondents' Consensus on Perceived Factors Influencing Tax Compliance

Table 5 shows that respondents generally agree (overall mean = 3.58, *Agree*) that multiple factors influence their tax compliance, reflecting a multidimensional motivation consistent with the literature.

Fairness and Simplification: Respondents strongly agree (3.60) that perceived fairness, a simple tax system, and easy implementation promote compliance. This aligns with research indicating that procedural justice, equity, and simplicity enhance voluntary adherence (Kirchler et al., 2008; MDPI, 2024).

Consequences and Enforcement: The highest agreement (4.12) was observed for compliance driven by automatic deductions, penalties, and legal consequences. This supports the "slippery slope framework," where enforcement complements voluntary compliance but is effective in deterring evasion (Wahl et al., 2010).

Responsibility and Citizenship: Respondents agreed (3.81) that awareness of civic duties, understanding taxation's necessity, and belief in its contribution to national development motivate compliance. This confirms findings that intrinsic motivations, or tax morale, significantly influence taxpayer behavior (Pacaldo & Ferrer, 2020).

Government Education and Trust: Moderate agreement (3.21–3.31, *Neither Agree nor Disagree*) was observed regarding compliance due to government education and trust. This suggests that while educational campaigns and visible accountability can influence behavior, respondents perceive gaps in effectiveness, transparency, or credibility, echoing literature emphasizing trust as a key determinant of voluntary compliance (Yip & Ho, 2021).

Materialized Government Projects and Services: Respondents agreed (3.42) that accessible services, infrastructure, and visible benefits from taxes encourage compliance. This highlights the importance of linking tax contributions to tangible outcomes, reinforcing perceptions of fairness, legitimacy, and the value of government services.

The findings suggest that compliance is influenced by a combination of procedural fairness, enforcement, civic responsibility, and observable government outcomes, with trust and education playing a moderate role. Effective public management should therefore ensure transparent use of funds, simplified procedures, visible projects, and consistent communication, balancing both coercive and voluntary mechanisms to enhance adherence and strengthen taxpayers' trust.

Relationship Between Perception of Philippine Income Tax and Adherence to the Canons of Taxation

Table 6 indicates a p-value of 0.292, which exceeds the 0.05 significance level, leading to the decision to fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_0). This suggests that there is no significant relationship between respondents' perception of the Philippine income tax system and their perception of its adherence to the classical canons of taxation.

The results further indicate a low correlation between these perceptions. Although respondents generally acknowledge the tax system and its components, this does not necessarily translate into a perception that the system fully complies with taxation principles such as equity, certainty, convenience, and economy. In essence, taxpayers may recognize the importance of taxation but still perceive gaps in fairness, proportionality, or procedural clarity.

This finding aligns with existing research emphasizing that tax compliance and perception are multifactorial, influenced not only by awareness of the system but also by trust in government, transparency, visible public services, enforcement, and fairness (Kirchler et al., 2008; Wahl et al., 2010; Pacaldo & Ferrer, 2020; Yip & Ho, 2021). It underscores the importance of public management practices—simplifying procedures, enhancing transparency, and linking taxes to tangible benefits—to ensure that taxpayer perceptions of the system correspond more closely with its adherence to classical taxation principles.

Public Management's Perceived Effectiveness and its Relationship to the Tax Compliance Rate

Table 7 examines how taxpayers' perceptions of public management effectiveness influence their compliance with personal income tax, using three compliance indicators. The findings show that the perception that taxes contribute to public interest projects consistently has a statistically significant relationship across all three indicators ($p = 0.000-0.002$), leading to rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates that taxpayers are more likely to comply when they perceive that their contributions result in tangible societal benefits, highlighting the critical role of visible government outcomes in motivating voluntary compliance (Pacaldo & Ferrer, 2020; Yip & Ho, 2021).

Other factors, including easy access to government services, perceptions of infrastructure projects, quality of government office services, and personal benefit from socio-economic projects, generally did not show significant relationships ($p > 0.05$). An exception was observed for the perceived quality of government offices influencing respondents' recognition of the need for continuous evaluation of the tax system (DV2-TC2, $p = 0.019$). This suggests that while convenience and service efficiency may influence perceptions, they are less consistently associated with actual compliance behaviors compared to the visibility of tax-funded projects.

These results indicate that taxpayers are primarily motivated by the tangible impacts of government projects rather than procedural or service-related factors alone. This finding aligns with the literature, which emphasizes that voluntary compliance is strengthened when citizens trust that their taxes are used effectively and benefit society (Kirchler et al., 2008; Wahl et al., 2010). While factors such as accessibility and office efficiency remain important for taxpayer convenience, they do not independently drive compliance as strongly as visible societal outcomes.

Overall, Table 7 underscores that perceived public benefit from taxes is the most critical factor influencing compliance, whereas service quality, convenience, and infrastructure visibility play secondary roles. Enhancing the visibility and communication of tax-funded projects can therefore strengthen voluntary compliance and trust in the tax system, supporting both effective public management and the principles of fairness and accountability in taxation.

Conclusions

The findings imply that effective tax compliance in the Philippines is strongly influenced by the perceived fairness of the tax system, the visibility of tax-funded projects, and the understanding of taxpayers' civic responsibilities. The significant impact of these factors suggests that policymakers and tax authorities should prioritize transparent governance, simplified procedures, and clear communication of how taxes benefit society. The evident link between public management effectiveness and voluntary compliance points to the need for adaptive, citizen-centered strategies that reinforce trust and accountability. These results also emphasize the importance of taxpayer education, as well-informed

citizens are more likely to recognize their obligations and participate actively in compliance. Overall, the study underscores that sustained commitment to transparency, efficiency, and public engagement is essential in strengthening voluntary compliance and enhancing the legitimacy of the Philippine tax system.

Recommendations

1. *Enhance Transparency and Public Communication.* The study highlights that taxpayers are most motivated to comply when they perceive tangible benefits from their taxes. Policymakers and tax authorities should prioritize transparent reporting and communication of tax-funded projects. This could include public dashboards, regular updates on infrastructure or social programs, and clear explanations of how taxes are allocated. Improving visibility of government initiatives can reinforce taxpayer trust, perceived fairness, and voluntary compliance.

2. *Simplify Tax Processes and Provide Support.* Respondents indicated that complexity in tax computation and filing, particularly for self-employed individuals, remains a barrier to compliance. It is recommended that the Bureau of Internal Revenue (BIR) simplify procedures, offer step-by-step guides, and provide workshops or online tutorials to help citizens better understand tax obligations, exemptions, and deductions. Enhanced accessibility through digital platforms should be complemented with personalized support for small businesses and individual taxpayers.

3. *Strengthen Taxpayer Education Programs.* While civic responsibility and awareness were positively associated with compliance, knowledge gaps were observed in tax computation and understanding exemptions. Tax authorities should implement continuous education and training programs targeting both youth and adults, integrating taxation concepts into higher education curricula and community outreach initiatives. This would foster long-term tax morale and informed participation.

4. *Promote Civic Engagement and Feedback Mechanisms.* The moderate perception of government responsiveness suggests the need for mechanisms allowing taxpayers to provide feedback and participate in policy evaluation. Surveys, focus groups, and public consultations can help authorities identify gaps, improve fairness, and strengthen procedural justice in tax administration.

5. *Future Research Directions.* Given the study's findings, future research could explore other taxpayer groups or larger, more diverse samples to verify trends across different regions or income levels. Researchers may also adopt mixed-methods or experimental designs, including intervention programs such as training workshops, public awareness campaigns, or digital simplification tools, to test their impact on compliance behavior. Unexpected or curious results, such as the low correlation between perception of the tax system and adherence to the canons of taxation, warrant further investigation to understand underlying causes and regional or demographic variations.

6. *Policy Implications.* Implementing these recommendations can lead to more effective public management, increased voluntary compliance, and stronger trust between citizens and the government. Strategic alignment of transparency, education, and visible service delivery ensures that taxpayers perceive the system as fair, accountable, and beneficial, ultimately strengthening fiscal sustainability and national development outcomes.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers affirm that this study was conducted in full adherence to ethical research standards. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to data collection, and participants were clearly informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any penalty or consequence. The anonymity and confidentiality of all respondents were strictly maintained, and all gathered information was handled in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The well-being and voluntary participation of the respondents were safeguarded throughout the process. The researchers declare that no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of this study, and plagiarism was rigorously avoided through proper citation and original analysis. All interpretations of the findings were made objectively and without bias, and the results were used solely for academic research purposes. The researchers also acknowledge that artificial intelligence tools were utilized only to assist in grammar refinement and formatting, while all core ideas, analyses, and conclusions were produced and validated by the researchers for full transparency.

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